

“OCEANIC CLIMATE SCAPES”: A REAL-TIME SONIFICATION OF CLIMATE CHANGE PHYSICO-CHEMICAL DATA APPLIED TO MARINE SOUNDSCAPES.

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ABSTRACT

Oceanic ClimateScapes explores creative sonification as a means to enhance understanding and empathy toward ecological changes in marine environments. The project examines the interplay between culture, nature and performance through sonification and algorithmic composition, utilizing new technologies such as electronics and programming. The performance maps four physicochemical parameters (pH, salinity, temperature, and water level) to sound transformations applied to marine soundscapes, recorded via hydrophones in the Hellenic Trench in collaboration with the *Pelagos Cetacean Research Institute* [1].

During the performance, climate data act as the "conductor" of the piece, with Arduino sensors collecting real-time input from a water beaker. This data is altered by gestural interventions and mapped to sound transformations. While sonification is inherently deterministic and scientific, integrating aesthetic criteria adds a new layer of meaning, positioning it as a form of algorithmic composition. Climate change is primarily anthropogenic in the Capitalocene Epoch, and in an analogy to sound, all these natural soundscapes become distorted and alienated from their original form. By engaging listeners with the sounds of the seas and oceans and how they are distorted through the sonification of changing physicochemical data, the aim is to inspire a sense of responsibility and action for the preservation of these vital ecosystems.

1. INTRODUCTION

Aquatic environmental degradation in the form of coral bleaching, ocean acidification, and melting of the polar ice cap among other issues, are some of the most significant environmental challenges of our time. They rank alongside deforestation, severe weather events, and species extinction [2]. Art has always been a driving force for social change throughout history, and to combat these environmental crises, art movements like ecological art [3] and acoustic ecology [4] have emerged in the late 1960s.

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Composers and sound artists have been contributing increasingly to biodiversity loss and climate change matters in recent years, enlarging the practice of environmental sound art. This experimental form helps reconnect people with nature, fostering educational and transformative experiences that align with care theories and aim for "more-than-human" coexistence [5].

All these natural disasters and the alteration of nature's data underscore the vital importance of interpreting global information—upon which countless human and non-human lives depend. Thus, developing effective ways to communicate this wealth of data is crucial, with artists playing a key role. In this project, sonification—the translation of data into sound—is employed as the primary technique. As Andrea Polli [6] observes, unlike physical materials, datasets are flexible representations that can be explored, processed, and transformed, offering unique interpretive opportunities. Through sonification, artists can evoke emotional responses that deepen environmental understanding and inspire action, a critical need to address global climate change.

Although research on sonification has grown, challenges persist in designing sounds that are both widely useful and aesthetically engaging for human-machine interaction. One key issue is the lack of a unified theoretical framework, combined with the natural limits of human perception and cognition. Consequently, researchers are calling for sonification techniques that effectively convey information while also appealing to the ear. For instance, Vickers and Hogg [7] emphasize the importance of aesthetics in sonification, and Polansky's notion of "*manifestation*" introduces an artistic approach that prioritizes the expressive quality of sound parameters over mere numerical accuracy [8]. Moreover, Van Ransbeeck [9] categorizes artistic sonification as a subset of algorithmic composition, effectively defining it as a form of music.

While environmentalism in performance spans different theoretical paradigms, from dualisms like Capitalocene/Anthropocene [10] to ecofeminist approaches that relate gender and environmentalism [11], the autonomy of technology in performance, especially in computer music and algorithmic composition, enables new forms of life where machines are independent of human agency. In this context, these performances invite listeners to engage in active, attentive listening [12] and raise awareness of the

underlying algorithms or artificial intelligence that may orchestrate them. Live algorithms and live coding represent different ends of human-computer interaction in algorithmic performances, but gesture remains a constant thread that unites the artist, audience, and technology. Gesture creates kinesthetic empathy, forging an embodied connection that redefines the relationship between art, mobility, and the environment. This interaction ultimately transforms sound into a shared movement within an auditory landscape, as the artist, technology, audience, and Earth itself converge through this immersive sonic experience [13].

The role of the artist in these auditory landscapes extends beyond merely translating data; they create rich sonic environments that expose the intricate dynamics of our ecosystems. In *Oceanic ClimateScapes*, real physicochemical data —i.e., pH, salinity, temperature, and water level— are measured from a beaker of water during the live performance, while the soundscapes sonified were originally captured in the Hellenic Trench. Not only does this performance record the sea’s evolving acoustic identity in the framework of climate change and environmental degradation, but also challenges the audience to rethink our place in marine ecosystems by integrating technology, science, and art to prompt reflection and action.

2. "OCEANIC CLIMATESCAPES"

"*Oceanic ClimateScapes*" is a performance that, as of the time of writing, has been realized twice and follows specific stages. These stages include:

- i. the collection of sound samples from marine soundscapes and their editing,
- ii. the process of mapping four climatic parameters to sound transformations and the creation of a ten-minute algorithmic composition – sonification,
- iii. the construction of a custom D.I.Y. Arduino Nano Sensor system [14] to receive real-time values and send them to a musical programming environment (Max/MSP),
- iv. a twenty-minute performance that incorporates the element of real-time sonification.

Several influential projects have shaped *Oceanic ClimateScapes* in its exploration of environmental performance, data sonification, and D.I.Y. systems for real-time sonification, particularly those with a focus on water. Yin’s "*Washing the River*" (1995) examines the ritual purification of polluted waters through performance [15], while works like "*Shield (2005–2006)*" [16], "*Acid Rain (2005)*" and "*Egyptian Chemistry*" [17] highlight the performativity of chemistry and frame *Nature* as *Culture*. "*Listening Underwater*" (2017) employs hydrophones in a performance aimed at raising ecological awareness [2]. Furthermore, projects that sonify physicochemical data, including "*Atmospherics/ Weather Works*" [18], "*N.*" [19] and "*The Climate Symphony*" [20], have paved the way for this approach. More recent initiatives such as "*WaterViz*" [21]

and "*WeatherChimes*" [22] emphasize collaborative, in-situ methods that integrate science, technology, and art for educational purposes.

2.1 Collection and Isolation of Sounds from Marine Ecosystems

This work began with the collection of environmental sounds from marine ecosystems in the Mediterranean Sea. Sonifying physicochemical changes in marine soundscapes presents a promising approach to enhance our understanding and appreciation of underwater environments, inviting listeners to engage with a largely unexplored acoustic dimension. The sound samples used were provided to the authors by research missions from the *Pelagos Cetacean Research Institute*. These are hydrophone recordings from previous years along the Hellenic Trench (from the west of Cephalonia to southern Crete). *Pelagos Cetacean Research Institute* has been operating since 1993, and its team of scientists has developed significant scientific activities with an international impact. It has collaborated with universities, research institutions, environmental organizations and international agencies in Greece and abroad, promoting research and the protection of marine mammals as well as their natural environment [1].

The Hellenic Trench is heavily impacted by seismic surveys, oil and gas extraction, and high shipping traffic. These activities, along with fisheries and extensive ecosystem changes driven by climate change, pose significant risks to cetacean populations that depend on this habitat. Given the region’s biodiversity and the vulnerable status of its marine species, Thompson et al. [23] advise caution when considering new permits for seismic exploration and hydrocarbon extraction across the broader Hellenic Trench area.

The recordings collected include sounds of the striped dolphin (*Stenella Coeruleoalba*, high-frequency whistles in the audible spectrum), successive blasts (resulting from the operation of seismic air guns used in research to locate hydrocarbon deposits), as well as the operation of military sonar guns. Additionally, sound was extracted from a video showing the socialization of a family of sperm whales (*Physeter Macrocephalus*), where the pulsed sounds heard (like small taps) are known as *codas*, a form of communication dialect among sperm whales.

The recordings had a significant amount of noise, primarily from passing vessels or the engine of the research vessel. On top of that, they capture the sound of the sea wave motion as the hydrophones move. To be able to isolate the sound sources from each recording, a light use of EQ, noise reduction, and other interventions was deemed necessary to improve sound clarity. The desired short sound samples from the initial recordings were trimmed for later inclusion in the composition. These include:

- the whistles of the striped dolphins
- the codas of the sperm whales
- the blasts from the seismic air guns

- a general sound background of the ecosystem indicating the underwater location (trimmed from parts of the recordings where the main sound source was silent).

2.2 Setting up virtual samplers, presets, and mapping climate-related physicochemical data to sound transformations (sonification)

Sonification in this particular project is based primarily on transformations performed on short-length sound excerpts derived from the said recordings, guided by some physicochemical parameters. These are *Temperature* (°C), *pH* (the negative logarithm of the concentration of H⁺ cations, which is a measure of the acidity of a solution), *Salinity* (the amount of salts in a volume of water, measured in units of psu, i.e., g/kg), and *Water Level* (in changes in cm). These parameters are recognized to undergo profound changes due to climate change in all the world’s oceans, as reported in recent official figures and studies [24, 25].

Approximate values for the mean global variations of these parameters were extracted from the above sources. These values were used as a reference framework for the sonification process in order to anchor the auditory transformations in real-world environmental change. However, the sonification maintains a creative scope and is not intended to provide a precise or literal acoustic rendering of the data. These values were taken as a starting point for sonification as shown in Table 1. The sonification technique used is parameter mapping (PMSon).

#	Physicochemical Parameter	Sound Variable
1	pH (↓8.2 - 7.7)	Speed, Pitch Shift
2	Salinity (↑20 - 50 g/kg)	FM Modulator
3	Temperature (↑15 - 20 °C)	Reverb
4	Water Level (↑0 - 6 cm)	Matrix

Table 1. Mapping of physicochemical parameters to sound variables.

Importantly, the goal of the composition was not to enable a listener to identify or interpret each individual sonified parameter. Rather, the focus was on creating a broad, conceptual sonic narrative—an abstract performance in which the original sound samples are gradually transformed, distorted, and detached from their source material, reflecting the overarching impact of environmental change. While parameter mapping was used as a structural tool, the broad approach was that of *creative sonification* [8]—a hybrid of sonification, artistic manifestation, and musical composition.

Within this framework, the composer intentionally did not follow a systematic or scientifically constrained method for mapping specific parameters to specific sound transformations. Instead, mappings were chosen in an intuitive and semi-random fashion, allowing aesthetic judg-

ment and expressive intent to guide which sonic processes (e.g., pitch shifting, fm modulation, reverberation, specialization) corresponded to changes in temperature, pH, salinity, or water level. This approach embraces ambiguity and subjectivity, favoring affective impact and perceptual transformation over analytical clarity.

The process of sonification was carried out using Max/MSP, specifically through its capability for presets, which allow for the storage of a “snapshot” of the transformations that sound samples undergo, depending on the changing parameter. All sound samples used, which were extracted during the first stage of editing, range from a few seconds to a couple of minutes in length. The changes in the four physicochemical parameters alter specific sound parameters or transform the sound of the sound samples in ways that are analyzed in the following subsections according to each physicochemical parameter. The aim is to create an algorithmic composition based on sonification, or in other words, a temporally organized sonification with the help of musical programming. Figure 1 shows the main patcher in presentation mode, consisting of several sub-patchers.

Figure 1. Main Max/MSP patcher in presentation mode with subpatches connected to a central matrix-main

2.2.1 pH

Changes in pH alter the sound samples of *Stenella coeruleoalba*, *Physeter macrocephalus*, and the background sound of the underwater soundscape. The pH varies from 8.2 to 7.7 in five distinct values, which correspond to five presets for the aforementioned sound samples. The changes in these samples occur in terms of pitch and playback speed, as detailed in Table 2.

#	pH (↓8.2 - 7.7)	Sample Play Speed	Pitch Shift (semitones)
1	8.2	1.00	0
2	8.07	0.50	-2
3	7.95	0.31	-5
4	7.83	2.00	6
5	7.7	-6.00	-2

Table 2. Mapping of pH to pitch and playback speed.

As pH decreases, indicating increased acidity, playback speed and pitch are adjusted to represent these changes in a perceptible auditory form. At pH 7.7, the negative playback speed (-6.00) reverses the sound, reflecting the maximum increase in acidity.

2.2.2 Temperature

Temperature changes were used here to modify the reverb applied to the Matrix. Reverb parameters, such as size, decay-time, high-frequency damping and diffusion, alter in response to rising temperatures, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Presets showing Reverbs’ characteristics alteration.

The objective was to shift the composition from the original audio samples in real space to a technically enhanced space with increasing reverberation. This extended decay time "blurs" the start and end of the audio samples, creating a sound that is more expansive and disordered than the original. The presets used here are seven, corresponding to seven temperature values, each ranging from 15 to 20 °C.

2.2.3 Salinity

The sonification of salinity introduces greater complexity, as both the composition and the performance have a temporal dimension. To enhance the system’s dynamics, salinity was introduced as a variable not from the outset, like the other parameters, but after a predefined interval when salt is actively added. Until that point, salinity remains constant at its initial value (20 g/kg) and has no impact on the sonic transformations within the system.

As the change initiates, it alters the preset and parameters of an FM modulator, which introduces sine, triangular, square, or sawtooth waveforms. Additionally, each preset undergoes modifications in both modulation frequency and modulation index. Similar to the reverb effect, the FM modulator is applied to the matrix, influencing the overall structure and integration of the individual sound samples. The corresponding mappings are presented in Table 3. As salinity rises, waveform complexity, modulation frequency and depth increase, creating more intrusive and distorted sonic effects that reflect environmental changes.

#	Salinity (g/kg)	Fm Modulator Parameters		
		Type	Mod. Freq. (Hz)	Mod. Index
1	20	cycle	1	1
2	27.5	cycle	5	10
3	35	triangle	20	10
4	42.5	rectangle	250	1.74
5	50	sawtooth	250	12

Table 3. Mapping of salinity to FM modulator parameters

2.2.4 Water Level

The Matrix, which is the second to last processor in the patch before the Stereo Out, essentially controls which channels will be played and with what stereo image (see Figure 3). As the water level rises, the density of the orchestration increases, both in terms of the number of sound samples and stereo width. Additionally, the matrix serves the overall purpose of the composition (i.e., the organized sonification over time), which begins with sparse, unprocessed orchestration and evolves into a dense, distorted one. Thus, the composition starts with the playback of just one sound sample and ends with the playback of all four sound samples, heavily layered with effects and distortion.

Figure 3. Matrix Mixer controls which samples play in L-R channels. The “Intervasion” sampler has three stereo outputs.

2.2.5 Exclusion of Seismic Airgun Sound Sample from Sonification

In the composition, the seismic airgun sound sample is introduced later, after the sonified transformations of other samples become clear. Unlike other samples, its presets evolve automatically without being linked to specific physicochemical parameters, incorporating microstructural composition and randomness. The sample generates three variations each time, with user-controlled presets adjusting playback-speed and decay (See figure 4). This approach distinguishes the artistic sonification of climate change parameters from the actual sound pollution caused by seismic airguns, which has been shown to disorient cetaceans [23].

Figure 4. Algorithmic sampler for the seismic airgun sound, generating three variations with evolving presets, independent of physicochemical parameters.

2.3 Arduino PCB Design and Max/MSP Integration for Real-Time Interaction

To implement the idea of real-time sonification of the physicochemical parameters of water, a microprocessor was required, which, after appropriate programming, could recognize these parameters and their changes with the help of sensors. In the realm of artistic performance, such sensors (such as those for pH or ion measurements) are rarely used. However, in the field of D.I.Y. chemical engineering, there are many sensors available for creating such a system, which can be connected electronically with Arduino, Raspberry Pi, and other similar microprocessors. By downloading the corresponding libraries they can also be programmed accordingly.

A D.I.Y. system, such as the one described here, utilizes electronic components connected to a specialized PCB (Printed Circuit Board), facilitating the integration of an Arduino Nano and four sensors, along with a small LED screen. A similar setup is recommended by Engr Fahad on his blog ElectroniClinic.com, where he provides various guides on constructing and programming D.I.Y. sensor and microprocessor systems with applications in engineering, science, and technology [14]. The specific configuration of the Arduino circuit and sensors employed in this study includes sensors for measuring temperature, pH, electrical conductivity/salinity, and water level. Initially, the specialized PCB was printed (see Fig. 5a) based on the circuit diagram, which specifies the necessary connections and components (transformers, transistors, capacitors, resistors, headers, etc.). All components were subsequently soldered onto the board (see Fig. 5b), and the necessary sensors were connected (see Fig. 5c). Several of these sensors consist of a main board and probe, such as the pH sensor, which requires calibration for proper operation [26]. Additionally, the temperature sensor (DS18B20 Temperature Sensor) is configured as a probe and necessitates a 330-ohm resistor between the data and VCC wire for proper functionality.

Figure 5. a) Printed PCB board according to circuit diagram. b) Components soldered onto the board. c) Sensors connected to the board.

During the programming phase, detailed code was written for each sensor, and selections were made regarding how often to record the values and which of them would be displayed on a small LED screen. Some changes were made to the initial code so that the measurements of the four sensors would appear on the Arduino IDE's "Serial Monitor" in the form of a list of four values every 4000 ms. In this format, the lists of values can then be recognized by Max/MSP using a sequence of objects such as `~zl group`, `~itoa`, `~fromsymbol`, and subsequently separate them into distinct values with `~unpack` to signal changes in the presets of the sonification mentioned above, at regular intervals chosen by the user. Figure 6 displays the main Max/MSP patcher in presenter mode after its integration with Arduino. This integration enables real-time alterations to specific sound parameters, shifting the approach from the structured parameter-mapping sonification (PM-Son) used in the first phase to a more creative and dynamic real-time sonification.

Figure 6. Max/MSP patcher after Arduino integration, enabling real-time sound parameter alterations.

2.4 Performance

Once the connection (through programming) between the input of physicochemical information and the output as

sound has been established, what remains is the execution by a human performer. After all, human intervention carries significant responsibility for ocean degradation, as evidenced by the changes in these parameters. The first performance lasted approximately twenty minutes and took place in the enclosed space of Π6 in Athens on June 22, 2024, while the second performance was slightly longer and took place at *Ov-Off Studio* in Athens on September 29, 2024.

In the practical aspect, an attempt was made to capture the physicochemical data using the four sensors placed in a beaker decorated as an aquarium, implying the presence of a marine ecosystem. The above data changes over time. The chemical parameters (pH and electrical conductivity/salinity) change slowly. During the performance, a bromothymol blue indicator is added. The pH changes as the performer blows into the water through a straw, causing the carbon dioxide from the exhalation to dissolve in the water as carbonic acid ions, which ultimately make the pH more acidic. Additionally, vinegar is gradually added, further decreasing the pH. The indicator color changes from blue to yellow as the solution becomes more acidic, with drops being added using a pipette. The electrical conductivity begins to change later, around the fourth minute of the performance, when a concentrated saline solution is gradually added using a pipette. Physical parameters (temperature and water level) change autonomously as the ice melts. Figure 7 shows two snapshots of the performances in the Π6 and *Ov-Off Studio* Spaces.

Figure 7. Snapshots from Π6 (left) and *Ov-Off studio* (right) performances

The live measurement data from the Arduino trigger an algorithmic composition that is based on the preceding sonification, which ultimately reaches the audience through a stereo speaker system. Whenever the performer allows, the environmental data can “play” the transformation of soundscapes, creating an interactive system. The sound samples from sonar guns used for hydrocarbon deposits produce noise pollution, and together with the sonification of the climate, they create a powerful commentary on the challenges facing the oceans.

Performances are divided into two approximately ten-minute segments, each utilizing different forms of interaction. During the first ten minutes, an auto-generated algorithmic process is unfolded based on the sonification data corresponding to parameters. The data lead the soundscapes from their raw form to a more transformed one, until the sound reaches a climax and gradually fades, signaling the second half of the performance. During this time, the performer prepares the beaker of water for the upcoming

measurements. In the second half, after pouring the appropriate solutions, with the press of a key, she instructs the system to take real-time measurements, incorporating the element of improvisation into the performance, while continuing to change the parameters with various gestures. The performer controls the real-time process, starting and stopping it at will, enhancing the interaction and enabling creative sonification.

After the end of the two performances, a link was provided to some attendees through which they filled out a feedback form regarding the performance. The texts collected, along with some verbal feedback that was shared after the performances, contributed to the conclusions regarding the impact of the performance on the audience. The feedback form is designed to give attendees the freedom to express their thoughts spontaneously in a small paragraph. The text was answered by approximately 10 people in total.

3. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In *Oceanic ClimateScapes*, the performance served as the culmination of an interdisciplinary investigation, integrating chemistry, electronics, computer science, and sound through artistic sonification with an ecological message. The primary objective was to present this sonification in a live setting, encouraging audiences to reflect on their emotional and intellectual responses. In many environmental sound art pieces, in-situ presentations—where the work is experienced within the environment it represents—play a crucial role in evoking emotional engagement. However, this project deliberately employed a simulated aquatic system rather than an actual marine setting to emphasize the human-driven distortion of marine ecosystems. This sonic distortion set the work apart from traditional soundscape compositions. In addition, due to the technological complexities involved, staging the performance in a real marine environment was impractical. Nevertheless, some audience members appreciated the contrast with the urban setting, noting that it offered a counterbalance to the sensory overload of city life and even contributed to stress reduction.

The performance raises the question of whether there is a distinction between raw noise pollution and the “artificial” distortion created through sonification, ultimately suggesting that both can serve as tools for environmental awareness. In particular, the sonic transformations in the latter half of the performance did not strictly adhere to proportional mathematical changes in the physicochemical parameters, as they were creatively interpreted. Structurally, the piece was designed as a twenty-minute performance with a clear beginning, middle, and end. It began with raw sound samples and initial physicochemical values, gradually evolving into a chaotic state where the original sources became unrecognizable due to extensive sonic transformations. This shift mirrors Schafer’s [12] concept of high- to low-fidelity soundscapes, transitioning from a natural marine soundscape to an artificial one dense with condensed sound information.

Audience feedback from *Oceanic ClimateScapes* sug-

gests that real-time sonification effectively conveyed both the marine environment and its sonic distortions. The attendees described the experience as immersive and musically cohesive, and many recognized the presence of seabed sounds and the relationship between sonic transformations and chemical changes in the beaker. Gesture played a key role in enhancing the sensory experience and fostering kinesthetic empathy between the artist and audience. An audience member remarked that “*the performance critically highlighted humanity’s reckless control over nature, which ultimately suffers under these actions. What started as curiosity soon felt like witnessing an impending catastrophe.*”

However, some listeners perceived certain segments of the soundscape as noise, which may have hindered their engagement. This reaction could stem from individual differences in perceptual sensitivity or from inherent challenges in the sonification design, as balancing clear data representation with aesthetic coherence remains complex. Suggestions for improvement included providing clearer visualizations of the chemical changes influencing the sound, as well as incorporating more dynamic physical gestures—such as movement or highlighting impactful chemical reactions—potentially involving a second performer.

The research concluded that while climate data sonification is rooted in a scientific and deterministic framework, the addition of aesthetic elements enriches the data, transforming it into a musically meaningful experience. Artistic sonification can thus be viewed as a subset of algorithmic composition, where the aesthetic aspect enhances the listener’s engagement. This work demonstrates how integrating aesthetic elements within climate data sonification can transcend purely scientific representation, creating an evocative and meaningful sonic narrative. By adopting a creative and intuitive approach to parameter mapping, the composition emphasizes emotional engagement and perceptual transformation rather than analytical precision. This method reveals the potential of artistic sonification to deepen our connection to environmental change through expressive soundscapes.

The *Oceanic ClimateScapes* system effectively raised awareness about ecological changes in marine environments driven by climate change. While the system aligns with NIME (New Interfaces for Musical Expression) principles [27], utilizing advanced sensors to enhance interactivity and expand musical possibilities, strong emphasis was also placed on adaptive, temporally evolving mapping that supports artistic expression. Although the sonification incorporated four live data points mapped to evolving sound samples, alongside improvisations during real-time interaction, most audience members engaged with the sonification as a holistic experience. Rather than focusing on identifying each parameter individually, listeners perceived the gradual transformation of the overall soundscape as a qualitative reflection of environmental change. This broad, evolving sonic narrative conveyed the ecological message clearly. The interplay between auto-generated processes and real-time interaction, with a clear distinc-

tion between them, appeared to enhance both the execution of the performance and the audience’s comprehension of the sonification. This was facilitated by customizable programming and direct integration between the electronic (Arduino) and musical (Max/MSP) software. Additionally, the emphasis on aesthetics in the composition and performance of the algorithmic music/sonification, along with the audience’s active engagement with their acoustic environment, further reinforced the overall experience.

Audience feedback discussed earlier offers valuable guidance for future work. In particular, future developments could focus on enhancing the clarity of sonification through multimodal representations, including synchronized visual display to support audience comprehension. Moreover, expanding the performative dimension—such as involving multiple performers or incorporating more pronounced physical interactions—could further deepen engagement and enrich the expressive potential of the system.

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